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Project economy as a new model for building sustainable business ecosystems in the digital environment

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***Abstract.** The article explores the transformation of economic systems from process-oriented management to a project-ecosystem model, emphasizing that the digital era is shaping a new architecture of value creation driven by knowledge, innovation, partnerships, and sustainability. The modern economy is increasingly networked, decentralized, and adaptive, forming the foundation of the Project Economy – a system where interconnected initiatives generate long-term value. The purpose of the study is to substantiate the conceptual foundations and to develop an integrative model for forming a sustainable project economy based on the combination of innovation development indicators and progress toward the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The theoretical framework relies on the concepts of Project Economy, the innovation approaches of the OECD, and the corporate sustainability principles of the World Economic Forum. The research employs comparative analysis, index evaluation, and structural-logical generalization methods, enabling the identification of interrelations between innovation potential and the sustainability of economic systems. The study proves that the efficiency of the national economy is determined by its ability to transform*

innovative resources (inputs) into sustainable outcomes through mechanisms of project management, digitalization, and cross-sectoral partnerships. Based on a comparative analysis of the SDG Index and the Global Innovation Index for 2025, it was found that Ukraine demonstrates a moderate level of innovativeness (66th in GII) and sustainability (42nd in SDG Index), while possessing significant growth potential driven by human capital, digital competencies, and international cooperation. The proposed author's Project–Sustainability Integration Model ensures the alignment of innovation outcomes with the implementation of the SDGs through project management mechanisms. It captures the synergy between technological progress and socio-economic stability, defining mechanisms for building a competitive, knowledge-based economy.

Keywords: *managerial architecture, adaptive ecosystems, digital tools, project maturity, innovation dynamics, sustainable growth, human capital.*

Проектна економіка як нова модель формування стійких бізнес-екосистем у цифровому середовищі

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Анотація. *У статті розглянуто трансформацію економічних систем у контексті переходу від процесно-орієнтованого управління до проектно-екосистемної моделі розвитку. Наголошено, що цифрова ера формує нову архітектуру створення вартості, де рушійною силою є знання, інновації, партнерства та стійкість. Визначено, що сучасна економіка втрачає ознаки лінійності й дедалі більше набуває характеристик мережовості, децентралізованості та адаптивності, що створює передумови для формування феномену проектної економіки – системи, в якій результат*

досягається через реалізацію взаємопов'язаних ініціатив, орієнтованих на довгострокову цінність. Метою дослідження є обґрунтування концептуальних засад і розроблення інтеграційної моделі формування стійкої проєктної економіки на основі поєднання показників інноваційного розвитку та досягнення Цілей сталого розвитку (ЦСР). Теоретичною базою слугували положення концепції *Project Economy*, інноваційних підходів *OECD* і принципів корпоративної сталості *World Economic Forum*. У процесі дослідження застосовано методи порівняльного аналізу, індексного оцінювання, системного та структурно-логічного узагальнення, що дало змогу визначити взаємозв'язки між інноваційним потенціалом і стійкістю економічних систем. У результаті доведено, що ефективність національної економіки визначається здатністю перетворювати інноваційні ресурси (*inputs*) на сталі результати через механізми проєктного управління, цифровізації та міжсекторних партнерств. На основі порівняльного аналізу *SDG Index* і *Global Innovation Index (GII)* за 2025 рік встановлено, що Україна демонструє середній рівень інноваційності (66-те місце в *GII*) та сталості (42-ге місце в *SDG Index*), водночас має значний потенціал зростання завдяки людському капіталу, цифровим компетенціям і міжнародній співпраці. Запропонована авторська модель інтеграції проєктів і сталого розвитку забезпечує поєднання результатів інноваційної діяльності з реалізацією ЦСР через механізми проєктного управління. Модель відображає системну синергію між технологічним розвитком і соціально-економічною стабільністю, визначаючи механізми формування конкурентоспроможної економіки знань.

Ключові слова: управлінська архітектура, адаптивні екосистеми, цифрові інструменти, проєктна зрілість, інноваційна динаміка, стале зростання, людський капітал.

Problem statement. In the context of global turbulence and digital transformation, the search for management models capable of ensuring flexibility, innovation and sustainability of business is of particular importance [1], as process-oriented approaches are gradually losing their effectiveness in an environment where speed of response and integration of digital technologies are becoming crucial. In response to these challenges, the Project Economy is being formed – a concept that considers projects as the basic unit of economic activity and defines a new logic of value creation. The relevance of the study is due to the need to combine innovative and sustainable development logics, since it is the synergy of technological solutions, environmental principles and social responsibility that ensures the ability of economic systems to self-renew [2, p. 95]. Digitalization, artificial intelligence, blockchain and data analytics form the basis for decentralized business ecosystems that operate on the principles of openness, partnership and self-regulation [1]. In this context, the understanding of the mechanisms for integrating innovation potential and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) within a single project paradigm is of scientific importance. Thus, the study is aimed at substantiating a new integration management model – project economics, which combines innovation, digital transformation and sustainability into a system architecture for the development of business and society.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Modern research reflects the evolution of approaches to combining digital transformation, innovation and sustainable development, which forms a new paradigm – a project-ecosystem model of growth. In this context, L. Blagodyr emphasizes that the formation of digital business ecosystems is the result of industry convergence and the influence of information and communication technologies, and their effectiveness is determined by such characteristics as modularity, openness, cooperation and network effects that ensure the joint creation of value for the consumer [3]. The idea is continued by L. D. W. Thomas, who considers the project ecosystem as an environment for

creating added value through the interaction of actors, where innovation is both a means and a result of cooperation [4]. Similarly, H.-T. Liao and co-authors define digital transformation as a catalyst for ecosystem innovations that support a «green» digital economy [5, p. 406]. Deepening this approach, A. Florek-Paszowska and A. Ujwary-Gil introduced the concept of the Digital-Sustainability Ecosystem, in which technologies – artificial intelligence, blockchain and the Internet of Things – play the role of strategic drivers of sustainable innovation [6, p. 116].

Their findings are supported by L. Zhang et al., who showed that combining digitalization and sustainability in project management reduces risks and increases the effectiveness of infrastructure solutions [7]. In summary, L. Espina-Romero and colleagues found uneven development of business ecosystems and the need for expanding interdisciplinary research [8]. A. Rifa'i and co-authors traced the thirty-year evolution of the concept of business ecosystems, noting the trend towards the integration of artificial intelligence, circular economy and platform management models [9]. This view is supported by Z. Liu and colleagues, who, comparing business, innovation and platform ecosystems, identified their standard features – openness, flexibility and diversity – as the basis for the adaptability of project structures [10]. In a socially oriented direction II. Pappas and co-authors emphasize the importance of responsible digital transformation that connects business, state and society to balance technological development and ethical values [11, p. 945]. Additional analytical depth was provided by L. Naeni and R. Tumpa, who identified key digital technologies – BIM, blockchain and cloud solutions – as factors for increasing project sustainability [12]. In Ukrainian realities, S. Gorban and O. Bilenko studied the formation of business ecosystems, emphasizing their fragmentation and the need for digital integration to achieve institutional maturity [13]. This logic is supported by O. Korobkova together with Z. Korobkova, interpreting customs logistics as a continuous process of managing flows in global supply chains, which is consistent with the principles of the project-ecosystem

approach [14, p. 177]. The legal aspect of this paradigm is reflected in the work of V. Savchenko and R. Maydanyk, who considered implied-in-fact contracts as a mechanism of trust and stability in interactions between economic entities [15, p. 283]. Complementarily, O. Lega and co-authors developed the ESG-BankruptIndex model, which combines financial and non-financial indicators to assess risks and enhance management sustainability [2, p. 95]. The review is concluded by the work of O. Korostin, who demonstrated the potential of artificial intelligence to optimize logistics processes and enhance innovation sustainability [16, p. 31]. The totality of these studies forms the methodological basis for creating an integration Project Sustainability Integration Model (PSIM), which combines innovation resources, project tools and sustainability principles into a single adaptive development ecosystem.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem. Despite the increasing number of scientific works devoted to the issues of digital transformation, innovation ecosystems and sustainable development, several aspects remain insufficiently researched. In particular, the mechanisms of integration between innovation and sustainable development indices need to be clarified, which would allow not only to assess the current state, but also to predict the potential for sustainable growth. Approaches to measuring the relationship between digital innovations, project management and socio-economic results are insufficiently developed. There is also a lack of systemic solutions for assessing the effectiveness of project activities in the context of global challenges – energy transition, technological competition and institutional adaptation of transition economies. Our research is aimed at the theoretical substantiation and practical development of an integration model for the formation of a sustainable project economy, based on a combination of innovation potential and sustainability indicators. Within the framework of this approach, special attention is paid to building a system of interaction between the GII and the SDG Index as an analytical basis for determining

the development trajectories of national business ecosystems in the digital environment. The practical significance of the study lies in the possibility of using the obtained results to improve state digital transformation programs, develop corporate sustainability strategies, create project maturity monitoring systems and assess the effectiveness of the implementation of the SDG in the business environment.

Formulation of the objectives of the article. The purpose of the study is to substantiate the conceptual principles and develop an integration model for the formation of a sustainable project economy based on a combination of innovation indices (GII) and sustainable development indicators (SDG Index), identifying the mechanisms of their interaction through digital platforms, partnerships, project management and human capital development.

Presentation of the main material of the study. In the era of global digitalization, economic approaches are being rethought: society is moving from functional logic to a project-ecosystem model of development. If previously the main task was to ensure stability, now the priorities are adaptability, creativity and the ability to create new value quickly [17, p. 58]. In this context, the phenomenon of the project economy is taking shape, where results are achieved through portfolios of interconnected projects that unite state, private and public initiatives for sustainable development. The transition to the project economy is due to a change like competition: linear structures are giving way to dynamic business ecosystems based on partnership, knowledge coordination and joint risk management. Such ecosystems combine flexibility, innovation, digital integration and social orientation, which ensures a rapid response to market and technological changes [17, p. 59]. Digital technologies play a leading role in the formation of the project economy, transforming it into a self-regulating network of interconnected initiatives. Artificial intelligence provides analytical support and risk forecasting, blockchain – transparency and trust between partners, and the Internet of Things – real-time

resource control [6, p. 120]. Their combination forms innovative ecosystems, where data exchange ensures sustainability, efficiency and openness to innovation. Thus, digitalization not only updates processes, but also defines a new management logic – the logic of project interaction.

International studies confirm that the project economy is becoming the leading model for organizing activities in the 21st century. According to the Project Management Institute (PMI) [18; 19], more than 60% of global GDP is created through projects, which demonstrates a shift in emphasis from operational stability to development. The World Economic Forum [20; 21] interprets it as an architecture of flexible sustainability that combines innovation with social responsibility, and the OECD [22] defines it as a tool for harmonizing economic, technological and social goals in the era of digital transformation. Therefore, project economics appears not only as a management approach, but as a comprehensive systemic model for the development of sustainable business ecosystems.

Further development of the concept of project economy requires its analytical understanding through the prism of objective indicators of innovation and sustainable development. It is quantitative indicators that make it possible to assess the extent to which national economies can combine technological growth, social responsibility and environmental balance - the three components that form the foundation of modern business ecosystems. For this, it is advisable to turn to an indicative assessment of the sustainability of economic systems, which is based on the results of the international ratings SDGs (SDG Index) [23] and Global Innovation Index (GII) [24]. Both indices reflect different but interrelated aspects of development. SDG Index measures the success of countries in achieving the SDGs according to social, economic and environmental parameters. At the same time, GII characterizes the potential of innovation activity, technological progress and digital maturity. A comparative analysis of these indicators makes it possible to determine how effectively countries integrate innovations into the system of sustainable project

management. In other words, it is about whether innovations become not an end in themselves, but a tool for achieving socially significant results: improving the quality of life, environmental safety, institutional stability and competitiveness of the economy.

The results of such a comparison indicate that sustainable business ecosystems are formed at the intersection of innovative activity and the ability to implement the SDGs [25]. To determine Ukraine's place in the system of relationships between innovation and sustainable development, it is advisable first to characterize the indicators of countries that are among the top ten world leaders according to the SDG and GII indices. These countries form the benchmarks of an effective project economy, where digital and technological solutions become catalysts for achieving the SDGs. Their experience confirms that high levels of innovation correlate with increased socio-economic sustainability, and investments in science, education and technology are the foundation of long-term competitiveness.

To illustrate this relationship, an indicative comparison of the SDG Index and GII indicators for 2025 for the European countries demonstrating the highest results has been made (table 1).

Table 1

Comparative characteristics of SDG Index and GII indicators, 2025

SDG Index, score	SDG rating	GII, score	GII rating	SDG achievement trend	Innovative capacity (GII)	Analytical characteristics
Finland						
87,0	1	67,5	6	High resilience in SDG 6, 7, 8; problems with SDG 13–15	Robust R&D infrastructure, innovation in clean tech	Leader of a balanced project economy: environmental sustainability + innovation
Sweden						
85,7	2	66,8	3	Strong positions in SDG 3, 7, 12; slowdown in SDG 13, 15	High level of digital innovation	Example of integrating a project approach into ecosystems of sustainable technologies

SDG Index, score	SDG rating	GII, score	GII rating	SDG achievement trend	Innovative capacity (GII)	Analytical characteristics
Germany						
83,7	4	64,9	7	Progress in SDG 8–12; stagnation in SDG 13, 15	High knowledge intensity, but bureaucratic barriers in project processes	Developed a project economy with a technological focus
France						
83,1	5	63,1	11	Average results in SDG 8–10; problems with SDG 13–14	Developed startup sector, weak cross-sectoral integration	Gradual shift in emphasis towards innovative projects with an ESG component

Source: based on [23; 24]

The analysis of the presented data indicates the presence of clear patterns in the development of countries with high indicators of innovation and sustainability. The countries of Northern Europe, in particular Finland and Sweden, demonstrate a harmonious combination of technological innovation and socio-ecological responsibility, which forms a balanced model of the project economy. Germany and France are distinguished by a stable combination of knowledge-intensive potential, developed infrastructure and socio-economic balance, which provides them with stable leadership positions in world rankings.

At the same time, the countries of Eastern Europe, including Ukraine, are currently at the stage of profound structural transformation, developing digital infrastructure, strengthening the project management system and enhancing international integration. It is such processes that create the basis for the formation of a competitive model of sustainable development.

In view of this, it is advisable to consider the profile of Ukraine separately, as it reflects a unique combination of dynamic development of individual sectors (energy, education, digitalization) with existing institutional and environmental challenges. It necessitates a detailed analysis of key sustainability indicators that determine the state's potential in forming a project-ecosystem management model

and integration into the global space of sustainable development (table 2).

Table 2

Profile of Ukraine according to the Sustainable Development Index, 2025

Indicator	Value	Comment
SDG Index Score, 2025	75,7	Average level of progress towards the SDGs; stable dynamics after 2023
Rank	42 / 166	Within the average group of countries in the Eastern Europe and Central Asia region
Region	Eastern Europe & Central Asia	Comparative assessment with Bulgaria, Georgia, and Poland
Spillovers Score (0–100)	92,0	High level of international interaction; positive contribution to global sustainable development chains
Regional Score (0–100)	72,0	Slightly lower than the average of OECD countries (80+), but higher than the average of all Europe
Percentage of missing data	3 %	Sufficiently complete statistical base for monitoring SDGs
Population (2024)	37.4 million people	The average size of the country in the region, which affects the scale of project implementation
Number of VNRs prepared	1	Voluntary national review of SDGs submitted to the UN

Source: constructed according to [23; 24]

According to the SDG Index 2025, Ukraine ranks 42nd out of 166 countries with a total score of 75.7, which corresponds to the average level of SDG implementation in the Eastern Europe and Central Asia region. This result demonstrates moderate progress in achieving the goals of economic growth, industrial development and partnership (SDG 8, 9, 17) and at the same time emphasizes the need to strengthen policies in the areas of health, climate action and institutional trust (SDG 3, 13, 16).

A positive fact is that Ukraine has a high international spillovers indicator (92 points), which indicates the country's active integration into global sustainable development initiatives and the expansion of project cooperation with international partners. The low level of missing statistical data (3%) confirms the sufficient maturity of the national SDG monitoring system, which provides an information basis for management decisions. However, the regional score of 72 indicates the presence of structural challenges in the socio-economic environment, which restrain

the pace of implementation of innovative and «green» solutions in production.

Thus, Ukraine's profile according to the SDG Index demonstrates a contradictory but promising development dynamics, combining significant international potential with existing internal constraints. Ukraine has all the necessary strategic prerequisites for the formation of a project-economic model of sustainable development. Still, the realization of this potential requires consistent strengthening of the institutional environment, development of the scientific and research base (R&D), as well as scaling of digital platforms and technological solutions focused on supporting sustainable initiatives and integration into the European innovation space.

Further research requires consideration of the innovative dimension of development, because it is innovation that determines the country's ability to transform socio-economic goals into specific project solutions. Suppose the SDG Index reflects the level of achievement of sustainable results. In that case, the GII characterizes the resource base, technological capacity and efficiency of transformation of knowledge into new economic value (table 3). The combination of these two dimensions makes it possible to assess the readiness of the national economy to implement the project management model in the digital environment.

Table 3

Profile of Ukraine by the Global Innovation Index, 2025

Indicator	Value	Comment
GII 2025 — overall ranking	66th place (out of 132)	Decline in positions compared to 2020 (45th place), explained by the impact of the war and structural challenges
Innovative resources (inputs)	80th place	Limited institutional stability, weak investment in R&D (0.3% of GDP)
Innovative results (outputs)	54th place	Above average: active digital developments, scientific publications, export of IT services
Best areas	ICT infrastructure (23rd place), education (48th place), scientific and technical creativity (30th place)	Strengths in education and IT export
Problem areas	Institutions (108th)	Insufficient quality of the regulatory

Indicator	Value	Comment
	place), environmental sustainability (91st place), investment (88th place)	environment and venture capital
Education spending (% of GDP)	2% (18th place)	Average level of public funding for education
Women with higher education, % of employment	30% (4th place)	One of the best indicators in the world, indicating gender balance in knowledge
Export of ICT services (% of trade)	10% (5th place)	One of the key drivers of innovation exports
Patents and utility models per \$ GDP (PPP)	33rd place / 1st place for utility models	High activity of small innovations and technical solutions
GDP (PPP, billion \$)	655.6	Average scale of the economy; requires design modernization to increase efficiency

Source: according to [23; 24]

For Ukraine, the innovation component is both a challenge and an opportunity. GII data for 2020–2025 indicate a gradual decline in the country's position (from 45th place in 2020 to 66th in 2025), which reflects the consequences of military and macroeconomic factors, as well as limited investment resources. At the same time, the structure of the index demonstrates an asymmetry between a low level of innovation resources (inputs - 80th place) and relatively higher innovation results (outputs – 54th place). It indicates high knowledge productivity and significant returns from the education and IT sectors even under resource constraints. A significant factor in the sustainability of Ukraine's innovation system is human capital. The country maintains high indicators in terms of the level of education funding (2% of GDP), higher education coverage (75.9%), and the number of specialists in science and technology. A high level of digital competence, growth in ICT services exports (10% in the structure of foreign trade) and leadership in the number of applicable models per unit of GDP indicate the potential for developing innovation and project ecosystems. However, a weak institutional base, insufficient venture financing and low efficiency of state regulation limit the possibilities of scaling technological initiatives. Thus, Ukraine's innovation profile

shows that the potential for the development of the project economy is based primarily on knowledge, creativity and digital competencies. At the same time, institutional and financial support need to be further strengthened.

The results of the analysis show that the combination of innovation potential with an orientation towards the SDGs is a key factor in the formation of a project economy in the digital environment. Taking this into account, the author's model «Integration of projects and sustainable development» (Table 4) was developed, which structures the primary levels of implementation of sustainable transformations – from the generation of innovations to the formation of ecosystem resilience. The table reflects the content of interaction, implementation tools, and expected results at each level of the model, demonstrating the logical sequence of development of the project economy.

Table 4

Structure of the Integration of projects and sustainable development

Level	Content of interaction	Main implementation tools	Expected effect
Innovations (inputs)	Generation of new knowledge, technologies, solutions	R&D, educational initiatives, venture financing	Growth of intellectual and technological potential
Projects	Institutional form of innovation implementation	Project management, Agile, digital management platforms	Implementation of strategic priorities, creation of added value
Sustainability results (SDGs) ESG reporting,	Socio-economic and environmental results of projects	SDG monitoring, and impact assessment systems	Reduction of inequality, rational use of resources, «green» transition
Ecosystem sustainability	Coordinated interaction of business, state and communities	Partner networks, digital interaction, public-private initiatives	Sustainable business ecosystems, competitive knowledge economy

Source: author's development

For a better understanding of the logic of the model's functioning, it is advisable to present its visual representation in the form of a diagram (fig. 1). It demonstrates the sequence of relationships between the levels of the model – from innovation as a source of new ideas to projects through which these ideas are

implemented, further to achieving sustainability outcomes and forming ecosystem resilience. Such visualization emphasizes the cyclicity, feedback loops and complementarity of processes within the project economy.

Fig. 1. Logic of the «Integration of projects and sustainable development» model's functioning

Source: author's development

The system functions as a continuous cycle in which the results of sustainable development generate new innovative ideas, and digital technologies, partnerships and knowledge management support sustainable connections between all sectors.

The proposed approach reflects the integration of innovation and sustainability, which is implemented through the digitalization of processes, the interaction of participants and the development of human capital. Its key components are digital platforms that ensure project coordination and data transparency, partnerships of the public, private and public sectors that contribute to the accumulation of resources and the spread of competencies, as well as human capital, which is the driving force of innovative change. In this way, not only is the sequence of stages of the development of the project economy demonstrated, but also the mechanism of its self-organization in the digital environment, which ensures the coordination of national strategies with the global SDGs and strengthens the

competitiveness of the economy.

Conclusions. The study confirmed that the transition from a process to a project-ecosystem model of development is a natural stage in the evolution of the modern economy in the context of digitalization. At the center of this transformation is the paradigm of the project economy, based on flexibility, innovation, digital integration and social orientation. It creates a methodological basis for the formation of sustainable business ecosystems, where economic efficiency is combined with environmental responsibility and social value. A comparative analysis of the SDG Index and GII showed that countries with high innovation indicators are achieving significant progress in the field of sustainable development. For Ukraine, this means that increasing innovation capacity is a key condition for the transition to a sustainable model of economic growth. Despite the existing institutional limitations, the country demonstrates positive dynamics in education, digitalization and international partnership, which creates the potential for the emergence of a European-type project economy. The proposed model, «Integration of projects and sustainable development», provides innovative results for the implementation of the SDGs through project management mechanisms. Its concept is based on the following relationships: innovation is a resource, projects are a tool, SDGs are a guideline, and ecosystem sustainability is a result. This approach ensures coordinated interaction between the state, business and society, forming the basis of a competitive and socially responsible economy.

Further research should be directed at quantitative verification of the PSIM model, development of project maturity indices and assessment of the economic return from the integration of SDGs into corporate and national strategies. It will allow empirically confirming the effectiveness of the project economy as a new model for the formation of sustainable business ecosystems in the digital environment.

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